

A Study of Visual Depiction of Ram Katha in Miniature Painting Traditions

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Abstract

Ram Katha holds a revered place in popular culture, where it's not only celebrated but also deeply embedded in worship practices. Passed down through oral traditions and vividly depicted in various visual art forms, the *Ramayana* narrative constitutes a rich body of interpretations and representations. From ancient sculptures to traditional paintings and folk styles, the varied facets of *Rama Katha* contribute to its multiplicity. Among these, traditional miniature paintings stand out, particularly in styles such as *Mughal, Rajput, Pahari, and Deccan*. Illustrated manuscripts of the *Ramayana* form a precious part of India's miniature painting heritage, reflecting its significance as a favoured subject alongside other Hindu texts. This paper attempts to study some of the visual representations of the text in traditional miniature styles to understand the concept of multiplicity across the genre

Key Words: Miniature Paintings, Ram Katha, Visual Traditions, Visual Depiction of Ramayana

Visual Interpretations of Ram katha

Practice of recitation of *Ramayana* narratives is prevalent as oral traditions in our country since ancient times. It also finds expressions in

manifold adaptations in our visual culture as well, such as the temple murals, *Mughal and Pahari* miniature paintings, folk masks and the illustrations.

The composition of two great epics of *Ramayana* and *Mahabharata*, in *Sanskrit* dates back to ancient time around Four Hundred BCE. *Ramayana* the older one became a Hindu compendium to social, moral, and religious traditions. The epic story of *Rama* existed before *Valmiki's Ramayana*, which is considered the earliest composition about the *Rama Katha*ⁱ. *Rama* the eldest son of Emperor *Dashrath* of *Ayodhya* was Crown Prince. He abandoned the throne to fulfil his father's promise to his stepmother and accepted the fourteen years of exile instead of ascending the throne.

Rama Katha has been interpreted in its modern adaptations in various parts of India, Southeast Asia, Central Asia, Cambodia, Iran, and Sri Lanka, and across the worldⁱⁱ. The *Ramayana* has a unique influence on Indian thought and art. It has widespread influences on the thought, belief, and culture of Indian peopleⁱⁱⁱ. Here existed an ancient oral tradition, of communication of magnificent epics and *Vedas* from one generation to another, preserved by memorizing and narrations, and transcribed centuries after the actual compilation.

Like oral and performing traditions of India, the visual traditions are also numerous in their manifestation. Visual traditions created their specific expressions with reciprocation to their oral compositions. These customs of graphical representation, whether plastic and figurative, developed after a long time of the development of oral traditions. The beautiful narrative of *Ramayana* has no doubt the strong possibilities of expression through various mediums in popular culture^{iv}. *Rama* in popular belief is incarnation of *Vishnu* and the

narrative is a story about this Incarnation of God who descended from Heaven, born on earth to perform *Lila*. This context creates a strong religious bonding with its readers and performers, listeners and viewers.

The visual traditions of *Ram Katha* are as diverse as the narrative traditions themselves, spanning various mediums and spanning centuries. From rock carvings in Kerala and Orissa to palm leaf manuscripts, temple wall paintings, textiles like the kalamkari tradition, and stone or wood carvings, the story of *Ramayana* finds expression in myriad forms. Before the era of printing, it was meticulously handwritten on paper, cloth, bark, and palm leaves. The oldest surviving illustrated manuscript dates back less than a thousand years. *Ramayana's* captivating narrative continues to be popular for illustrations, showcased in elaborate festivals nationwide. Artists, sculptors, woodcarvers, painters, musicians, and dancers alike resonate with *Ram Katha*, leading to its proliferation on temple walls, frescoes, scrolls, and textiles. These visual representations enrich the collection of *Rama* Narratives, reflecting the cultural beliefs, social dynamics, and historical contexts of the people who created them.

Iconography and Depiction of the Narrative

Despite efforts to discern influences, continuities, and similarities among different visual traditions, a standardised figure in the iconography of *Rama Katha* remains elusive. Artists from different backgrounds interpret and depict the narrative of *Rama Katha* in unique ways, resulting in a multitude of representations. While maintaining individuality, each artist manages to craft a recognizable character. In the Kullu hill tradition, *Rama* emerges as a primal forest inhabitant, adorned with a skirt and a leafy crown. Contrastingly, Akbar's royal *Ramayana* portrays *Ravana* as a majestic emperor, adorned with opulence

and sporting ten regal heads. In the *Mewar* atelier, *Ravana* takes on a troubled visage, reminiscent of Mughal influences. Meanwhile, artists from *Guler*, *Kangra*, and other hill states envision *Ravana* with a beard and surrounded by peculiar demons.^v In *Mewar*, the artist *Manohar* occasionally depicted *Rama* with a moustache, while *Hanuman* was often portrayed as a wild, untamed monkey, a common motif. Meanwhile, artists from the hill regions meticulously distinguished between the forest and the garden, selecting identifiable trees such as bananas and cypresses for their settings.^{vi}

Mewari painters favoured hills over plains, creating distinct landscapes. Diverse traditions excel in expressing varied contours and expressions uniquely. Scenes from the *Yuddha Kanda* painted in *Mewar* and the painting *Siege of Lanka from Guler, Kangra* drawing show, the remarkable difference in drawing of figures as well as the treatment of the subject and vividness of expression and the technique, distinguishes these visual traditions.^{vii} These visuals show the process of imagination of characters and their surroundings, here figures embody some components of the artist's immediate reality also.

Miniature paintings beautifully capture adaptations from the *Ram Katha* legend, with numerous illustrated copies of the *Ramayana* preserved in libraries and private collections worldwide. These manuscripts illuminate the evolution of India's different artistic schools. Originating centuries ago, miniature painting flourished during the *Mughal* era and continued under regional rulers in *Himachal, Rajasthan, Bundelkhand, Malwa, Ahmednagar, Golconda, Tanjore, Orissa*, etc., evolving unique styles influenced by geography and patronage.

Manuscript Illustration of Ramayana under Akbar

Miniature painting reached its pinnacle in *Akbar's* Imperial court, where he commissioned translations and illuminations of native texts like the *Ramayana*. Copies, including one in *Sawai Man Singh Museum, Jaipur*, and another in *Freer Gallery, Washington*, were created for wider dissemination. As *Akbar* was keenly interested in the translation of *Hindu* texts into *Persian* language from *Sanskrit*, he also ordered sumptuous ornamentation of these translated manuscripts.^{viii} A translated and adorned manuscript from *Akbar's* court was part of his mother *Hamida Banu's* collection. External patrons, unable to access the Imperial workshop, supported artists who replicated Mughal Court paintings, hinting at Hindu patronage.^{ix}

Folio from illustrated manuscript of *Ramayana*, *Death of the King Dashrath* (Fig.1) in the Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York, depicts the mourning scene of King *Dashrath's* death. Three queens and attendants' express grief through untied hair and raised hands. Intricately patterned textiles and original Sanskrit texts suggest Hindu patronage, unlike Persian translations ordered by Akbar.^x

Mughal painters took guidance from Hindu iconography and textual prescriptions when they developed a specific iconographic plan for presenting central characters and Hindu deities, but they altered the characteristics and appearance of divine figures. *The Freer Sackler* and *Jaipur Ramayana* were both painted in a consolidated iconography that overcame the challenge and problem of incorrect identification while preserving the significant characters in their most characteristic form. In the Mughal miniature painting, depiction of *Ram* and *Lakshmana* is often as that of warriors with bows, wearing traditional

indigenous clothes and a cummerbund, adorned with flowers. Several deities like *Indra*, *Brahma*, *Shiva*, *Vishnu*, and *Hanuman* are rendered wearing a royal costume and crown. *Sita* is painted wearing *Rajasthani* traditional dress. *Hanuman* is painted in princely costumes and crown and is identifiable by his distinct appearance. The courtiers are painted, wearing Mughal attire resembling that of the period of Akbar with a long coat or dress with a round skirt tied on the right side, and a pair of tight trousers and a colourful cummerbund with the dagger and a turban. A folio from the collection of Jaipur Museum, illustrates *Ram*, *Lakshmana*, and *Sita* received by *Nishad King*. *Ram*, *Lakshmana* and *Sita* after they have shunned royal attires, are rendered as ascetic. While the *Nishad* king and his subjects are wearing Mughal-styled dresses along with headgears. *Ram* after leaving *Ayodhya* with his brother and wife reached the bank of *Ganga*. Here the *Nishad* king is receiving him and offering gifts. In the traditional depiction, *Ram* receives gifts under a fig tree as per the text. However, the Freer Manuscript portrays *Ram* and *Lakshmana* in regal attire. *Sita* is absent, with *Brahma*, *Vishnu*, and *Shiva* witnessing. The river *Ganga* holds prominence.^{xi}

Mughal artist rendered *Sita* sensitively and delicately as she was considered as Incarnation of Goddess *Lakshmi*, consort to God *Vishnu* whose incarnation is *Ram*. Where *Ram* is regarded as *Maryadapushottama*' embodying his dutiful character, in the epic *Sita* echoes the embodiment of virtues of an ideal woman and wife. She follows her husband during exile thus, she is presented as an extremely loyal character, but *Ravana* depicted as *Rakshasa* King with ominous and demonic characteristics, abducted her, therefore she, falling prey to his lustful wish although never succumbing to his desires and

protecting her chastity and ultimately was led to her unfortunate self-sacrifice. ^{xii} *The Abduction of Sita by Ravana* (Fig.2) from the Freer Collection best demonstrates this strong character of *Sita*. Artist presents *Sita* in petite size in contrast to the gigantic stature of *Ravan* with ten heads and twenty arms, shown as demon King, thus rendering the feeble condition of *Sita*. The yellow background of barren land, suggests a pensive atmosphere, a state of melancholia and remorse. The background acts complimentary to the central characters ^{xiii}.

Rajput Miniatures- Illustrated Manuscripts of Ramayana

Rajput miniature artists celebrated *Rama* as the incarnation of *Vishnu*. Worship of *Rama* was enormously practised and considered imperative for religious practice. Therefore, *Ramayana* continued its widespread sacred and popular appeal among Courts and common people. *Rajput* miniature painting flourished at various centres like *Udaipur*, *Jaipur*, *Kota*, *Bundi*, *Jodhpur*, *Kishangarh* and others, of which *Mewar* or *Udaipur* was the most significant and creative centre for miniature painting where Illustrated manuscripts of *Ramayana* were painted around seventeenth century along with other substantial miniature paintings^{xiv}. The illustrated manuscripts of *Ramayana* are in collection of *Prince of Wales Museum, Bombay, British Library, London, Rajasthan Oriental Research Centre, Udaipur*. The significant characteristic of these miniatures painted in manuscripts is the bold outline drawings, vibrant palate and several consecutive scenes in one frame. These illustrated manuscripts are intricate containing many components and took several years for completion.

Sahibdin in order to include every episode of narration, tried to raise the viewpoint on the bird's eye view, thus creating the temporal or spatial sequences. Therefore, he was not painting the narrative freeze, instead, his illustrations followed the Indian traditional convention of simultaneous narration. The same character or characters can appear several times within the one frame to indicate either spatial or temporal progression within the story. An illustration explaining his use of the device is painting of *Baharat and Shatrughan taking leave of their Parents*. It is a simple example showing locations within the palace and the two princes going between them, so involving both spatial and temporal progression.^{xv} *Sahibdin's* style with a mixture of popular Mughal and traditional Rajasthani local idiom using bright hues contrasted near each other, excelled in techniques and draughtsman ship, While *Manohar* with his bold and decorative palate charmed the visitor The painting, *Ram and Lakshmana on command of sage Vishwamitra kill Tadaka* with beautiful depiction of foliage exemplifies the style of *Manohar*. While the painting, *Rama severed the Body of Kumbhkarna*. (Fig.3) depict the huge body of *Kumbhkarna* severed by *Rama's* Arrows crushes down to earth against the yellow background of battlefield shows the influence by the painting by Deccan.

Ramayana Manuscripts of Malwa Style

Ramayana manuscripts in the *Malwa* Style are housed in *Bharat Kala Bhawan, Varanasi, and Kanoria Collection, Patna*. *Dr. Anand Krishna* distinguishes two sub-styles within *Malwa miniatures*: one marked by vibrancy and the other by distinguished pictorial expression. Folios from these collections are vibrant and dynamic, belonging to the first style^{xvi}. Typically

lacking inscriptions on the painting, short one or two-line statements in Bundelkhand dialect appear on the reverse, indicating the folio's theme. The relationship between the written word and painted image in the manuscript is explored due to the narrative nature of the Ramayana text.^{xvii} Influenced by popular performances like *Ram Lila*, artists infused the paintings with a performative quality. Gestures are harmoniously coordinated, and facial expressions are heightened, amplifying the sense of enactment. This influence is particularly evident in the depiction of demons, portrayed with comedic exaggeration rather than inducing fear.

Pahari Miniature of Ramayana Series

The *Pahari Ramayana* miniature series are technically less complex but there is delicacy in the outline and scheme of colours used. *Bahu (Jammu), Guler, Kangra, Chamba, Basohali* were the prominent centres where the art of miniature painting culminated in *Pahari* Regions and obviously, *Ramayana* was favourite theme for painters. A Painting *Portrait of Rama* from Basohali shows *Ram* seated on a lotus with thousand petals. The large pages depicting the segment of the epic known as *The Siege of Lanka*, were created in Punjab Hills, Guler, in the mid eighteenth century, the illustrations show the treatment of the episodes that immediately precede the great battle between the armies of *Rama* and *Ravana*, as well as the battle itself. In one of the picture *Ravana shows the Counterfeit Head of Rama to Sita* (Fig.4) attributed to *Manku*, *Sita* appears seated alone in the garden where *Ravan* holds her hostage. She resisted *Ravan's* advances. The multi headed, multi armed *Ravana* approaches her and his demon servant holds a severed head that looks exactly like *Rama*. *Sita* bows her head

in grief, but continues to be true to her husband. While all other figures in the composition are attached to elements of architecture or trees or to one another, *Sita* sits alone, isolated against the plain green ground of the garden. The water in the foreground of this and other paintings reminds us that the episode takes place at the island.^{xviii} Throughout the epic, readers are invited to compare the upright nature of Rama and his family to the decadent and impulsive behaviour of Ravan and his followers.^{xix}

A Folio from the Second *Guler Ramayana* series to *Aranya Kanda* from *Guler Rama and Lakshmana at the Hermitage of Sage Agastya*, shows a peaceful setting with lush trees and lavish landscape. Here in this calm and serene environment nestles the hermitage of Sage *Agastya*. *Ram* accompanied with *Sita* and *Lakshmana* are approaching the beautiful hermitage led by an ascetic. The sage with dignified gestures is shown receiving his guests. There is clarity in the rendering of the forest setting and the hut with its scarce belongings.^{xx} The Beautiful Painting from *Kangra*, *Ram and Sita in Exile* show the three royal children dressed with leaves, have made their home in wilderness. The precisely finished picture depicts the peaceful impression.

Many *Ramayana* paintings were painted in *Kullu* near *Mandi* and *Kangra*. The *Ramayana* series well known as *Shangri Ramayana* was painted towards the end of the seventeenth century and the earlier series was not painted at *Kullu* but at *Bahu* in *Jammu*. A folio from the *Shangri Ramayana* series *The Monkey Army takes on some Demons* is possibly from the court of *Bahu*. The scene depicts the battle between the well-armed demons riding on chariots and the group of *Vanaras*, from *Rama's* army holding rocks and uprooted trees, yet

determined to win. The distinguishable characteristic is crudeness of the workmanship, absence of the use of gold, flat background.^{xxi}

The elaborated examples of the illustrations of *Ram Katha* in various miniature traditions, suggest that the Epic story have been adapted profoundly for the visual depictions. It has the capacity to connect to people's emotions and this involvement varies across regions, depending on class, religion, caste, ethnicity, and gender. Hence, it gave the visuals a varied character. Because of this great possibility of connecting with everyone's sentiment, its depiction shifts beyond the social and geographical borders. It was adapted, and narrated in different cultures with different viewpoints for diversified audiences who can share emotional bonding with the story from different levels of personal or social experience. Therefore, artists in different styles have created characters vividly and they have depicted the visuals communicating the narrative sentiment in their indigenous manners. Although they were able to retain the uniqueness of persona of the characters of *Ram Katha* in almost every tradition.

Rama imagery tends to emphasize the values that the god embodies like steadfast honour, courage and responsibility, depiction of the *Rama* theme must be considered against the background of not only literature and the development of the art of miniature tradition but against the backdrop of the value system, which it represents and the ideals it places before individuals for norms of human conduct. Visual depiction of *Ram Katha* in its multifaceted form not only represents a wealth of cultural multiplicity but also the conception and development of the unique visual character of a common native belief system that had an ability to spread far and wide and inspire the common man.

Pictures for Reference

Fig.1.The Death of King Dashratha, the Father of Rama, Folio from a Ramayana
Date: ca. 1605, Medium: Opaque watercolour and gold on paper, H. 10 1/2 in. W. 5 13/16 in.
Courtesy, Met Museum.

Source page

<https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/454359?rpp=20&pg=6&ao=on&ft=akbar&pos=102>

Fig.2. Abduction of Sita, Folio from the Ramayana of Valmiki (The Freer Ramayana), Vol. 1, recto: Ravana Seizes Sita by the hair to abduct her to Lanka; verso: 1597-1605 Painted by Shyam Sunder, Mughal dynasty; Opaque watercolor, ink, and gold on paper H: 26.4 W: 14.3 cm Northern India, Courtesy: Rare Book Society of India,

Source Page

<https://scroll.in/article/684556/Eight-exquisite-Mughal-miniatures-of-the-Ramayana-commissioned-by-emperor-Akbar>

Fig.3. Ram Severed Body of Kumbhkarna. Plate 92. Courtesy: Losty, J. P. The Mewar Ramayana Manuscripts. British library.

Fig.4. Ravana Shows Counterfeit Head of Ram to Sita. Attributed to Manku. From the Illustrated, the Siege of Lanka, Series. Guler. Opaque watercolour and gold on paper.

H.60.3cm. W. 82.7cm. Ross- Coomarswamy Collection. Plate 61. Courtesy, Cummins, Joan. Indian Painting. Courtesy Museum of Fine Arts, Boston.

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